

**MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY AMONG HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS ON
VEGETARIAN AND NON-VEGETARIAN DIET IN NIMS HOSPITAL JAIPUR,
RAJASTHAN, A CROSS SECTIONAL, OBSERVATIONAL STUDY**

Ms. Sadiya Shokat^{1*}, Dr. Gaurav Kumar Khandelwal², Dr. Shaurya Mehta³, Dr. Pratik Tripathi

^{1*} Assistant Professor, Department of Dialysis Technology, NIMS College of Paramedical
Technology, NIMS university Jaipur

² Associate Professor, Department of Nephrology, NIMS Hospital Rajasthan Jaipur

³ Assistant Professor, Department of Nephrology, NIMS Hospital Rajasthan Jaipur

⁴ Professor and Head Department of Nephrology, NIMS Hospital Rajasthan Jaipur

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ABSTRACT

Background: - Animal based protein is of high biological value and plant-based protein is of low biological value, which can interfere with the recommended dietary protein intake and probably the quality of life. In hemodialysis patients low biological value proteins are capable of causing protein energy wasting which can increase the morbidity and mortality in patients on hemodialysis.

Methods: This 6-month cross-sectional observational study involved 20 patients selected by specific criteria. Monthly assessments included anthropometry, dietary intake (via food frequency questionnaire), and lab tests (hemoglobin, WBC count, serum albumin, total protein, urea, creatinine, potassium, phosphorus). Subjective Global Assessment was done quarterly. Quality of life, infection rates, hospitalizations, and blood transfusion needs were also recorded.

Results: - Total number of patients on vegetarian diet were 8 out of which 5 were male and 3 were female and patients on non-veg diet were 12 out of which 8 were male and 4 were female. There was no significant difference in demographic characteristics at initiation of study (age and gender). Statistically significant difference noted in dietary calorie intake, dietary protein intake and serum potassium level between the groups and it was higher. The infection rate was 1 among vegetarian patients and 2 among non-vegetarian patients. Emergency hospitalization occurred in 1 out of 8 vegetarian patients and 2 out of 12 non-vegetarian patients.

Conclusion: - The study found that patients receiving adequate twice-weekly dialysis and maintaining high protein and calorie intake—regardless of being non-vegetarian—had similar quality of life and morbidity. Overall, the findings emphasize that nutritional quality and effective dialysis are more important than the protein source.

Key words: Hemodialysis, dietary protein intake, dietary calorie intake, protein energy wasting, nutritional assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic renal disease is a crucial public health issue faced by >2 million people world-wide [1]. Maintenance Hemodialysis (MHD) is a procedure which is done in end stage renal disease (ESRD) patients for removal of uremic toxins, balancing electrolyte disturbances and better quality of life (QOL) [2,3]. Adjustment of dietary intake is crucial in patients with ESRD on Maintenance Hemodialysis (MHD), which involve low phosphorus, potassium and sodium and sufficient calorie and protein intake for upholding a stable health [4]. Because not sticking to the advised diet, leads to life threatening health issues i.e., fluid overload, electrolyte imbalance or worsening of existing symptoms and limits the benefits of ongoing Renal Replacement therapies (RRT) [5]. Although, continuity of these strict dietary adjustments can cause low protein consumption and loss of appetite or anorexia is a common condition seen in ESRD patients undergoing hemodialysis leading to malnutrition [6,7,8]. Protein Energy Wasting (PEW) is correlated with reduced functional capacity, increased morbidity along with increased possibility of infection and extended hospitalization [9]. It is more widespread in MHD than in pre-dialysis phase, because of intradialytic protein wasting [10]. Considering this, it is advised to elevate the dietary protein intake following the initiation of dialysis [11]. So, for the patients on MHD protein-rich animal products or plant-based protein such as soybeans are advised to meet their higher protein requirements [12]. Because of its higher concentration of amino acids and ability to transport additional elements like calcium and iron, animal-based protein is superior to plant-based protein in terms of nutrition. [13].

The updated recommendations by Kidney Foundation Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative (KDOQI) 2020 for energy intake for patients on MHD are 25-35kcal/kg/ and 1-1.2g/kg proteins per day [14].

The biological value, net protein utilization and protein digestibility is more in animal protein than in plant-based protein [15]. But they have been seen to be insignificant in some clinical studies [16]. As they may cause metabolic imbalance, acidosis and nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, further deteriorating the health [17, 18]. Also, by enhancing the dietary protein up to the recommended guidelines, will directly lead to increased phosphorus intake [19]. Because a high-protein diet is among the most abundant sources of phosphorus and hyperphosphatemia is an issue of big worry in patients with ESRD on maintenance hemodialysis [20,21]. However, over 50% of the dietary protein should come from a high biological value source, which is essentially animal-based protein, under the K DOQI nutrition standards [22]. And “high protein diet = animal derived protein = best protein” is till now the base prescription [23]. And according to a survey done by PEW Research Center only 39% of the Indian population is on vegetarian diet [24]. Due to this diverse dietary pattern, it's reasonable to expect a significant difference in protein and calorie intake among various cultural and religious groups.

Similarly, at NIMS Hospital Jaipur, individuals from diverse cultural and religious backgrounds come for hemodialysis therapy, each with their own dietary patterns. Therefore, we conducted a study to evaluate the survival and quality of life of hemodialysis patients following mixed (animal and plant-based diets) and veg (plant-based) diets.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design and recruitment: -

This was a hospital based, observational cross-sectional study. It was conducted in the Hemodialysis unit of Department of Nephrology NIMS Hospital Jaipur, Rajasthan for 6 months, from the month of January 2024 to June 2024. Patients were recruited based on the inclusion criteria:

1. Patient's age more than 18 years old
2. On MHD for more than 6 months.

And the exclusion criteria were:

- i. Patients with any mental disabilities that made them unable to understand and answer the questionnaire.
- ii. Patient with proven cardiovascular disorders / Cerebrovascular disorders.
- iii. Previous known case of haemoglobinopathy in patients.
- iv. Active infection on recruitment.

Study procedures: -

All enrolled patients' baseline information, such as their gender, age, body mass index (BMI), dietary patterns, vascular access, primary cause of renal disease and dialysis vintage was collected. Height and weight were recorded, and ideal body weight was estimated according to standard adult BMI guidelines based on the patients' height and dry weight. The BMI ranges commonly used in India are [25]:

- a. Underweight: BMI < 18.5 kg/m².
- b. BMI 18.5 to 22.9 kg/m² is considered normal weight.
- c. BMI 23.0 to 24.9 kg/m² indicates overweight.

Participants were categorized into two distinct groups based on their dietary preferences: those following a vegetarian diet and those following a non-vegetarian diet. The study involved monthly clinical evaluations, including patient history, physical examination, and relevant biochemical investigations such as CBC, serum albumin, total protein and RFT (serum urea, creatinine, potassium, phosphate) for 6 months. Nutritional status was assessed monthly through dietary intake using a food frequency questionnaire, at the end of each month to capture the dietary habits over the entire month. Detailed caloric and protein intake data were collected and compared to the recommended dietary guidelines for hemodialysis patients. Nutrient intake adequacy was evaluated to determine if participants met the dietary requirements essential for

managing their condition. This study also utilized a set of key anthropometric measurements to assess the nutritional status and physical health of patients on hemodialysis. BMI, height, weight, and mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) and triceps skinfold thickness were among these parameters. MAUC <25 cm for males and <24 cm for females can be considered a simple alternative for detecting undernutrition in adults. While the Subjective Global Assessment (SGA) was performed every three months. These evaluations offered a thorough insight into the patients' overall health and nutritional condition during the study period. Meaning of different parameters over 6 months was evaluated and compared between both groups to assess the potential influence of vegetarian and non-vegetarian diets on the overall health and well-being of hemodialysis patients. Morbidity and mortality were assessed by recording the number of infections, hospitalizations, and deaths, and these were systematically compared across the two dietary groups

Statistical analysis: -

Total no. of patients (n)= 20

The sample size was based on convenience sampling.

Convenience sampling is a qualitative research method where participants are chosen based on how easily they can be accessed and their willingness to participate.

Data was entered in MS EXCEL 2019. Data was analyzed using software SPSS v23. (Freely available software). As continuous variables, the mean and standard deviation were employed. T-tests for independent samples were performed. To ascertain whether there is a statistically significant difference between two independent groups, the means of those groups are compared using the independent sample t-test. And p value was calculated to find a significance difference between 2 groups i.e., patients on vegetarian diet and patients on non-veg diet. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed to indicate statistical significance in the data.

Results & Discussion

Adequate nutritional assessment, including dietary protein and calorie intake, is crucial for maintenance hemodialysis patients due to their elevated risk of protein-energy malnutrition (PEM). Protein and calorie intake can significantly vary based on individual dietary preferences, particularly with two primary protein sources: vegetarian diet and non-vegetarian diet.

This study compared the outcomes of maintenance hemodialysis patients on vegetarian versus non-vegetarian diets to see if dietary preferences influenced survival and quality of life. It was expected that vegetarian patients would have lower protein intake but might benefit from lower unhealthy fats, higher fiber, and lower phosphorus levels, which could improve gut health, blood sugar levels, and reduce serum nitrogenous waste.

The study at hand provides a detailed analysis of various biochemical, nutritional, and clinical parameters in a small sample of patients following vegetarian and non-vegetarian diets. The key findings indicate significant differences in daily dietary calorie intake, protein intake, and serum potassium levels between both groups, while other parameters didn't show any significant differences. To contextualize these findings, it is essential to compare them with data from other

A. Baseline Characteristics				
	Vegetarian		Non-vegetarian	
1. No. of patients according on the basis of dietary preferences	8		12	
	Male: - 5	Female: -3	Male: - 8	Female: - 4
2. Mean age of patients	38.7±15.52 (ranging 18-63)		44.4±12.51 (ranging 25-70)	
3. Causes of ESRD				
i. Hypertensive nephropathy	n=11			
ii. AKI	n= 3			
iii. Congenital	n= 3			
iv. Diabetic Nephropathy	n= 2			
v. Nephrolithiasis	n= 1			

studies exploring the impact of vegetarian and non-vegetarian diets on similar health markers.

Table.1 Baseline Characteristics of patients on Vegetarian and Non-Vegetarian diet.

Number of patients included in the study were 20, Table 1 presents the clinical and baseline characteristics of all the patients. For this study patients were divided into 2 groups on the basis of their dietary preferences in vegetarian and non-vegetarian. Number of patients on non-veg diet was greater than the number of patients on veg diet. Total number of patients on a non-veg diet was 12 with 4 females and 8 males. And the total number of patients on veg diet was 8 in which 3 were females and 5 were males. The mean age of patients on a veg diet was 38.7 ± 15.52 (ranging 18-63) and the mean age of non-veg patients was 44.4 ± 12.51 cc. The reason for ESRD was hypertensive nephropathy (n=11), acute kidney injury (n=3), diabetic nephropathy (n=2), congenital (n=3) and nephrolithiasis (n=1).

To evaluate the morbidity and mortality between these two groups, daily dietary caloric and protein intake, Hb, serum urea, creatinine, phosphate, potassium, total protein, albumin, BMI, SGA and anthropometric measurements were recorded for duration of 6 months which is

B. Clinical Characteristics	Vegetarian	Non-vegetarian	p Value
1. Dietary intake			
Dietary Calorie Kcal/day	953 \pm 186.2	1061 \pm 247.4	p= 0.0008
Dietary Protein g/day	41.64 \pm 6.41	54.83 \pm 18.69	p= 0.04
2. Biochemical Parameters			
Serum Urea mg/dl	144.4 \pm 49	122.8 \pm 18.27	p= >0.05
Serum creatinine mg/dl	11.1 \pm 2.28	10.2 \pm 1.64	p= >0.05
Serum phosphorus mg/dl	6.2 \pm 1.46	5.89 \pm 1.78	p= >0.05
Serum potassium mmol/L	6.6 \pm 1.89	5.1 \pm 0.66	p= 0.04
Serum total protein g/dl	6.7 \pm 0.55	6.4 \pm 0.4	p= >0.05
Serum albumin g/dl	3.93 \pm 0.54	3.95 \pm 0.3	p= > 0.05
Hemoglobin g/dl	9.3 \pm 2.2	8.5 \pm 0.85	p= > 0.05
3. Nutritional Parameters			
Body mass index kg/m ²	19.8 \pm 6.11	19.7 \pm 3.8	p= > 0.05
Skinfold thickness mm	11 \pm 5.4	9.4 \pm 6.63	p= > 0.05
Mid-Upper Arm Circumference cm	22 \pm 3.22	22.7 \pm 2.63	p= > 0.05
Subjective Global Assessment	B	B	

represented with mean \pm standard deviation.

Table.1 Difference Between mean Biochemical parameters and dietary intake and nutritional parameters of patients on Vegetarian and Non-Vegetarian diet.

In this study, 24-hour dietary recall showed that only 6 out of 12 patients on non-vegetarian diet were able to stick to the optimum dietary protein and calorie intake as advised by KDOQI, i.e., 25-35kcal/kg/ and 1-1.2g/kg proteins per day. And in the vegetarian group 5 out of 8 patients

were

Graph 1: Mean Dietary Intake

able to achieve daily dietary calorie and protein intake of > 30 kcal/kg/day and >1.2 g/kg/day. Also, there was a significant difference between the Dietary calorie intake ($p= 0.0008$) as well as dietary protein intake ($p= 0.04$) between patients on vegetarian diet and non-vegetarian diet respectively. The comparison between Dietary intake, biochemical Parameters and nutritional parameters between the 2 groups are given in Table 2.

Difference between the Dietary calorie intake ($p= 0.0008$) as well as dietary protein intake ($p= 0.04$) between patients on vegetarian diet and non-vegetarian diet respectively. The comparison between Dietary intake, biochemical Parameters and nutritional parameters between the 2 groups are given in Table 2.

In biochemical parameters no significant difference was seen in serum urea, serum creatinine, serum Phosphorus, serum total protein, serum albumin and hemoglobin level in patients in the vegetarian group and no vegetarian group. But serum potassium level was notably lower in

patients

Graph 2: Biochemical Parameters

on mixed diets (non-veg) diet as compared to patients on veg diet ($p= 0.04$). Lab value of Serum Potassium was >6 mg/dl in patients on vegetarian diet, due to larger intake of plant-based diet and protein, which can lead to hyperkalemic conditions as given in table 1.2 and graph 2

The serum phosphorus level was measured to determine whether patients on a vegetarian diet or those on a non-vegetarian diet have higher serum phosphorus levels, given that plant-based diets are typically high in phosphate content but no significant difference was seen in both groups. Although there were 10 patients out of 20 with serum albumin level of ≥ 4.0 g/dl which is target range for serum albumin for patients on HD by KDOQI Guidelines.

For measurement of Nutritional parameters in both groups BMI, Skin fold thickness, MUAC and Subjective global assessment tests were done in both groups and the study revealed there was no difference present in nutritional parameters across two groups ($p > 0.05$) as shown in table 2 and graph 3. Mean BMI of both the groups was more than 18.5 kg/m^2 , which is considered as normal weight. A low BMI might have indicated insufficient calorie intake and risk of malnutrition. MUAC was <25 in both groups (22 ± 3.22 in veg group and 22.7 ± 2.63 in non veg

group) as shown in graph 3, which represent mild undernutrition. For SGA both groups were in B category which indicates moderately malnourishment as given in table 2.

Graph 3: Nutritional Parameters

Morbidity risk between patients on vegetarian (veg) and non-vegetarian (non-veg) diets was assessed on the basis of 3 criteria. These criteria are as follows:

Incidence of infections: were higher in non-vegetarian patients as compared to patients on veg diet.

Need for blood transfusion: - was higher in non-veg patients. It is noteworthy that most blood transfusions for non-veg patients were administered predominantly in May.

Incidence of emergency admissions: - Incidence of emergency admissions were higher in non-veg group and the most common cause of emergency in both groups was fluid overload and shortness of breath

Incidence of death: - Remarkably, there was one incidence of death in non-Veg groups. As given in table 3.

Criteria	Veg	Non-Veg
Incidence of Infections	1	2
Need for Blood Transfusion	0	3
Incidence of Emergency Admissions	1	2
Incidence of Death	0	1

TABLE 3. Morbidity and Mortality

DISCUSSION

This study compared survival and quality of life outcomes in hemodialysis patients adhering to vegetarian versus non-vegetarian diets to determine the influence of dietary preferences. It was expected that mixed (non-vegetarian) diet would result in higher protein and calorie consumption, consequently lowering the occurrence of PEW and enhancing patient's quality of life.

The study at hand provides a detailed analysis of various biochemical, nutritional, and clinical parameters in a small sample of patients following vegetarian and non-vegetarian diets. The key findings indicated a significant difference in daily dietary calorie intake ($p = 0.0008$), protein intake ($p = 0.04$), and serum potassium levels ($p = 0.04$), with the vegetarian group being hyperkalemic. This may be attributed to increased dietary phosphorus and potassium from plant-based foods. However, a prior study reported that vegetarian patients on HD had reduced protein intake but showed no difference in energy intake or serum potassium levels, and vegetarian patients were not associated with hyperkalemia [26]. Another study found equal protein and calorie intake between the two groups, but lower phosphorus intake in vegetarians [27]. An additional study noted lower protein and phosphorus intake in plant-based diets compared to animal-based [6]. But, in this study, serum phosphorus levels showed no significant difference (vegetarian: 6.2 ± 1.46 vs. non-vegetarian: 5.89 ± 1.78), possibly due to inadequate protein intake in both groups

In this study we also looked to see if dietary preferences affect the hemoglobin level and anemia conditions, as red meat and animal-based diets are rich sources of heme iron. But no significant difference in hemoglobin levels was found, 3 out of 12 non-vegetarian patients required blood transfusions. A past study reported lower serum ferritin in vegetarians due to reduced iron stores [28], and another showed that well-planned vegetarian diets could meet iron requirements via non-heme sources and fortified foods [29]. Serum urea and creatinine are important maker of renal functioning and were expected to be higher in patients with animal-based diet but in this study no significantly different was seen (urea: vegetarian 144.4 ± 49 vs. non-vegetarian 122.8 ± 18.27 , $p > 0.05$; creatinine: vegetarian 11.1 ± 2.28 vs. non-vegetarian 10.2 ± 1.64 , $p > 0.05$). Although other studies have shown lower blood urea nitrogen and creatinine in vegetarians mostly due to not achieving recommended dietary intake [12], and that, vegetarians had lower serum creatinine, protein intake, lean body mass, and grip strength [30]. This study may not reflect those findings due to financial constraints limiting protein and energy intake in both groups. Some individuals who were initially consuming a substantial non-vegetarian diet may have had to reduce their dietary protein and energy intake due to financial constraints, as they were unable to afford animal-based protein.

No significant difference was present in mean S. total protein, mean serum albumin, mean body mass index and nutritional parameters between both groups. A previous study noted significantly lower levels of biochemical markers including Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN), phosphate, creatinine, normalized protein catabolic rate and serum albumin in vegetarian group ($p < .05$) [31], Serum albumin level of $<3.8\text{g/dl}$ is often considered as an indicator of increased risk for protein energy wasting, and in our study patients of both groups were not able to achieve a serum albumin level of 4g/dl . In this study Nutritional assessment using skinfold thickness, MUAC, and SGA found no significant differences, with both groups classified as moderately malnourished (SGA score B). This aligns with findings from another study showing lower mid-arm muscle circumference and BMI in vegetarians ($p < 0.05$), with similar SGA scores across both groups [32].

The infection rate was 1 among vegetarian patients and 2 among non-vegetarian patients. Emergency hospitalization occurred in 1 out of 8 vegetarian patients and 2 out of 12 non-vegetarian patients. Mixed diet groups (non-vegetarian) groups exhibited a greater need for blood transfusion compared to vegetarians. Despite the general higher iron and vitamin B12 content in non-vegetarian diets, patients needed blood transfusion due to overall poor health condition because of ESRD per se. More research is required to understand why non-vegetarians have lower hemoglobin levels. A single mortality was recorded in a patient within the non-vegetarian cohort. This patient had a history of long-standing maintenance hemodialysis and exhibited refractory ascites, which, along with other unspecified conditions, may have contributed to this outcome. Similarly, a previous study showed similar outcomes that increased intake of plant protein compared to animal protein is associated with improved quality of life HD patients [33].

CONCLUSION: This study suggests that patients receiving twice-weekly adequate dialysis, achieving and maintaining higher protein and calorie intake in non-vegetarian, showed the same quality of life and morbidity irrespective of their dietary habits. The results indicated that multiple factors—such as dialysis effectiveness, inflammation levels, financial conditions, and the severity of the disease—affect patient outcomes. Overall, the study highlights that adequate dialysis and good nutritional intake play a more critical role in health outcomes than the specific source of dietary protein.

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